

Probability Grouping and Shannon's Entropy

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 12, 2023

Shannon's entropy is given by $-\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ where $P(i)$ is the probability for the state i . The question is: What is the state i ? In particular, different choices of the states in question lead to different entropies. Traditionally, the states associated with a gas with no degeneracy in energy levels are those for which energy E is distributed among N particles, with each distribution carrying the same weight. The number of permutations of a specific $\{n(e_i)\}$ set is: $N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!$ where $\sum_i n(e_i) = N$ and $\sum_i e_i n(e_i) = E$ (or Eaverage for a sharp distribution) may map into different physical configurations with different pressures. For example, an arrangement of three e_1 's followed by 4 e_2 's may not be the same physical situation as 1 e_1 , 2 e_2 's, 2 e_1 's 2 e_2 's. In other words, there may be a pressure related reason for choosing states.

If each distribution carries the same weight, then $\ln(1/\#\text{arrangements}) = \ln(\text{Probability of the average scenario of } N \text{ particles})$. For N large, $n(e_i) = Np(e_i)$ where $p(e_i)$ is single particle probability for independent particles. Then the average probability corresponds to: $\prod_i (p(e_i))$ [to the power of $Np(e_i)$]. $\ln(\text{average probability}) = \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) + \ln(N)$. $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ is then the Shannon's entropy of the gas for no degeneracy in energy levels. The degeneracy in energy levels also seems to assume an average $n(e_i)$ for each e_i as we discuss in this note (following (1)) i.e. considering boson and fermion cases where again the idea of pressure related states appears.

In (2) it seems that a different grouping of probabilities is made to define physical states. (2) suggests that single particle situations which have the same number of $n(e_1)$, $n(e_2)$, $n(e_3)$.. etc i.e. specific sets $\{n(e_i)\}$ such that $\sum n(e_i) = N$ and $\sum e_i n(e_i) = E(\text{average})$ should be grouped together i.e. have their probabilities summed. Thus all permutations of the same set of $n(e_i)$'s are grouped into one probability and this is used to compute Shannon's entropy i.e. $\text{Probability} = N! / \prod n(e_i)! \prod p(e_i)$ [to the power $n(e_i)$]. No degeneracy in energy levels is considered and ultimately Maxwell-Boltzmann distributions are used for single particles. This then leads to a different entropy than using the $p(e_i)$'s corresponding to the average picture (i.e. average of all the equally weight distributions of E over N). Arguments are made that this entropy allows for $-\ln(N!)$ to disappear as $T \rightarrow 0$ as all particles drop to the ground state. For $S = -\ln(N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!) , T \rightarrow 0$ also means that the MB distribution no longer holds and that $n(\text{ground state})=N$ and so S also tends to 0.

Shannon's Entropy Depends on the Probability Distribution Used

Shannon's entropy is defined as:

$$S = -\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i)) \quad ((1))$$

The question is: What is i , the level? If one considers a fair die with 6 sides, a physical state may be the side which appears after a toss. Then $p(i)=1/6$ which yields a certain S . If on the other hand, one removes information, i.e. only considers even or odd die toss results, one has

P(even), P(odd) for the same die, with each being .5. This may be used in ((1)) and yields a different result from $p(i)=\frac{1}{6}$. Thus the question seems to be: What states should be used for a gas which has independent single particles with energies which have no degeneracy?

What States Should be Used When Creating Probabilities?

Traditionally, a gas of independent particles is described by distributions of a total energy E over N particles. This is called the microcanonical distribution. If one relaxes the condition of total energy E and considers an average energy $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i = E(\text{average})/N$ where a very sharp distribution is associated with $E(\text{average})$ then this is an approximation to the microcanonical case called the canonical. An assumption made is that each distribution of E over N particles has the same weight, where the particles are considered indistinguishable.

A question which seems to arise is whether one should consider various distributions of E over N which have exactly the same $n(e_1), n(e_2), n(e_3) \dots$ values as representing their own probabilities as they may represent different local pressure distribution.

In (2) probabilities of different permutations of the same set of $n(e_1), n(e_2), n(e_3)$ etc are summed together to create the probability{ specific $n(e_i)$ set} i.e.

$$\text{probability}\{\text{specific } n(e_i) \text{ set}\} = N! / \text{Product over } i \ n(e_i) * \text{Product over } i \ p(e_i)^{n(e_i)} \quad ((2))$$

This probability ((2)) is then used in Shannon's entropy to obtain equation ((14)) of (2) i.e.

$$S = N (\text{Single Particle Entropy}) - \ln(N!) + \sum_{\text{over } l} \langle Nl \rangle \quad ((3))$$

where $\sum_{\text{over } l}$ is over allowed $n(e_i)$ sets and:

$$\langle Nl \rangle = \sum_{n=0, N} (N \text{ choose } n) p(l)^n (1-p(l))^{N-n} \ln(n!) \quad ((4))$$

Maxwell-Boltzmann distributions $C \exp(-e_i/T)$ are used for $p(e_i)$ with $n(e_i) = Np(e_i)$.

We question whether one should sum over various permutations of the same set of $n(e_i)$'s to create a single probability. If a permutation of $n(e_i)$'s maps to a distribution in space, then each permutation is physically measurable because it leads to different local pressure scenarios. In such a case one may question the grouping of all permutations unless there is a physical reason that nature does not distinguish between these.

Traditionally, instead of using ((2)) one assumes equilibrium single particle probabilities $p(e_i)$ with $n(e_i) = Np(e_i)$ for N very large. This leads to:

$$\text{Probability}(N \text{ very large}) = \text{Product over } i \ p(e_i)^{Np(e_i)} \quad ((5))$$

$$\ln\{\text{Probability}(N \text{ very large})\} = \sum_{\text{over } i} N p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((6))$$

Here $p(e_i)$ are the single particle probabilities which would be measured in an equilibrium situation. The probability ((6)) should equal:

$$\ln \left[\frac{1}{\{\# \text{ permutations of the equilibrium } \{n(e_i)\} \text{ set}\}} \right] = \ln \left\{ \frac{\text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)!}{N!} \right\} \quad ((7))$$

In ((7)) $n(e_i) = Np(e_i)$ i.e. N is large. This still does not indicate what specific set of $\{n(e_i)\}$ is used in ((7)) to represent the equilibrium picture. In fact, one extremizes ((7)) with respect to the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E(\text{average})/N$. Thus a very special set of $n(e_i)$'s (or $Np(e_i)$ s) applies to ((7)). ((7)) is linked to the number of permutations of the special set of $\{n(e_i)\}$ i.e. the equilibrium set. There is no grouping of these to represent one probability, in fact, $-\ln(\# \text{ permutations})$ of the special set of $\{n(e_i)\}$ gives the entropy. Thus the set of $\{n(e_i)\}$ seems to represent a kind of maximum-average scenario. This set $\{n(e_i)\}$ may be used to calculate average energy, even though there may be fluctuations to this average.

For example, one may perform measurements by making a small hole in a container of gas and measuring the velocities which come out. On average one sees the set $\{n(e_i)\}$ emerge. Even though one does not distinguish the order in which the e_i come out when calculating $n(e_i)$, the order or permutations are key in creating the # permutations which lead to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution which experimentally verified for large N in a gas. They also may represent pressure distributions. Thus we argue that these permutations should be distinct and in fact, the entropy is:

$$-\ln \left(\frac{N!}{\text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)!} \right) = -\ln (\text{permutations of the special } \{n(e_i)\} \text{ set}). \quad ((8))$$

Low T Limit

In (2), it is noted that the single particle entropy (using Maxwell-Boltzmann probabilities) becomes very small as $T \rightarrow 0$. This leaves $-\ln(N!)$ and the sum of ((4)). For $T \rightarrow 0$, all particles should tend to the ground state, so $p(l)=1$ and $1-p(l)=0$. Furthermore $n \rightarrow N$, yielding $\ln(N!)$ which cancels the $-\ln(N!)$ term.

If one examines the entropy created from taking the \ln of the number of permutations of the special $\{n(e_i)\}$ set, then one has:

$$-\ln \left(\frac{N!}{\text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)} \right) \quad ((9))$$

In the low T limit, $n(\text{e ground state}) \rightarrow N$ and the rest of the $n(e_i) \rightarrow 0$ with $0! = 1$. Thus $-\ln(1)$ is left in ((9)) and this too vanishes in the low T limit, but in this case the $\exp(-e/T)$ distribution no longer holds. We note that in (1), $N! / \text{Product over } i \ n(i)!$ is divided by $N!$ as a "rule" to obtain the "correct Boltzmann counting".

Energy Level Degeneracy

Although ((2)) does not deal with degeneracies in energy levels, we consider results presented in (1) which deal with them. In this case, it is no longer the $-\ln$ of the permutations of

the special set of $\{n(e_i)\}$ which govern entropy. A special set $\{n(e_i)\}$ still exists, but there is a degeneracy g_i for each i state with all degeneracy levels having energy e_i . N .

For the case of bosons, one may consider n identical particles each with energy e_i in a level with g_i degenerate boxes. One may permute box walls minus 1 with the n particles to find the total number permutations within a level i.e.

$$(n(i) + g(i) - 1)! / \{n(i)! (g(i) - 1)!\} \quad ((10))$$

Thus with degeneracies present it is no longer $\ln(n(i)!)$ which is the important term (which is linked with the permutations of the special set $\{n(e_i)\}$), but rather the arrangements within the degenerate boxes in each level i . These arrangements become a sum when one takes \ln . Thus N does not even appear as one relaxes the constraint that one has N particles to $\langle N_{\text{average}} \rangle = N$ as in the canonical approach. In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, we argued that different permutations of the special set $\{n(e_i)\}$ possibly represent different local momenta i.e. the arrangements map to spatial positions. In the boson case, the degeneracy in a gas usually comes from the momentum vectors $(2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot n_x / L, 2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot n_y / L, 2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot n_z / L)$ which have the same magnitude. These represent momentum vectors pointing in different directions and each of these impart momentum. Thus maximizing arrangements in the degenerate cells seems to again be linked to pressure (impulse hits). As a result, there may be an underlying physical idea to the $\{n(e_i)\}$ special set in terms of pressure.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that different probability schemes yield different Shannon's entropies as is well-known. Thus, one needs to determine which probabilities to use in a problem. In (2), it is suggested that for an energy E distributed over N particles, one use the probability:

$$\text{Probability} = N! / \text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)! \ \text{Product over } i \ p(e_i)^{n(e_i)} \quad ((A))$$

$p(e_i)$ are single particle probabilities and taken to be of the Maxwell-Boltzmann form. As a result, the probabilities of all permutations of any specific $\{n(e_i)\}$ set are summed to create a grouped probability. This is then used in an expression for Shannon's entropy and it is seen that the result is: $N \text{ Entropy}(\text{single particle}) - \ln(N!) + \text{Sum over possible results } (N \text{ choose } n) p(i)^n (1-p)^{N-n} \ln(n!)$. It is argued that for $T \rightarrow 0$, Entropy (single particle) goes to 0 and $-\ln(N!)$ cancels with $\ln(N!)$ from the last term because $p(i)$ becomes 1 for the ground state.

We argue that traditionally there is a special $\{n(e_i)\}$ set which maximizes the number of permutations: $N! / \text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)!$ subject to the constraint $\text{Sum over } i \ e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}}/N$. These permutations may physically represent different pressure arrangements in space. The entropy is then \ln of this expression. Thus it may not be necessary to collapse the probabilities as in ((A)). We note that the idea of a special set $\{n(e_i)\}$ also exists in the boson case for which one maximizes the arrangements within degenerate boxes within a fixed i level with all particles in that level having e_i . The degenerate boxes are usually associated with momentum vector directions and so again one again maximizes so to speak a kind of pressure distribution. Thus there may be a physical reason to choosing the states in a problem linked to pressure.

Finally, we note that $\ln(N! / \text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)!) \text{ at low } T \text{ goes to } 0 \text{ if all particles tend to the ground state i.e. } n(\text{ground state}) = N \text{ and the other } n(e_i)'s = 0 \text{ with } 0! = 1. \text{ This means one no longer has a MB distribution as } T \rightarrow 0.$

References

1. Huang, K. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1987)

2. Spalvieri, A. The Exact Entropy Formula of the Ideal Gas and its Information Theoretic Interpretation (2023)

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2305.04652.pdf>